

1 **Running head:**

2 **Macro- and micronutrient pool in post-fire wood**

3 **Title:**

4 **Charred wood remaining after a wildfire as a reservoir of macro- and**
5 **micronutrients in a Mediterranean pine forest**

6

7 *Sara Marañón-Jiménez^{A,B}, Jorge Castro^{A,C}, Emilia Fernández-Ondoño^D, Regino

8 Zamora^{A,C}

9 (A) Grupo de Ecología Terrestre. Departamento de Ecología, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Granada, E-18071

10 Granada, Spain

11 (B) Department Hydrosystemmodellierung, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH – UFZ, 04318 Leipzig,

12 Germany

13 (C) Centro Andaluz del Medio Ambiente (CEAMA), Av. Del Mediterráneo s/n, E- 18006 Granada, Spain

14 (D) Departamento de Edafología y Química Agrícola. Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Granada, E-18071

15 Granada, Spain

16

17 *Corresponding author. E-mail: smaranon@ugr.es

18

19

20

21

22

23

24

25

26

27

28 **Abstract:**

29 Large amounts of logs and coarse woody debris remain in the ecosystem after wildfires.
30 However, the relevance of the nutrient reservoir contained in the remaining post-fire
31 woody debris for the ecosystem nutrient reserves is rarely considered. In this paper, we
32 determine the C and nutrient concentrations in the partially charred wood after a
33 wildfire along an altitudinal gradient and assess the relative magnitude of the nutrient
34 reservoir in the wood in relation to those existing in the first 10-cm soil layer. Soils
35 were poorly developed and nutrients limiting for the vegetation requirements. Charred
36 woody material still contained a relatively high concentration of nutrients compared to
37 those reported for unburnt pine wood, and in general, this decreased with altitude.
38 Partially charred wood represented a considerable pool of nutrients, due to both the
39 relatively high concentrations and to the great amount of biomass still present after the
40 fire. Potential contributions of the charred wood were particularly relevant for N and
41 micronutrients Na, Mn, Fe, Zn and Cu, as wood contained 2-9 times more nutrients than
42 the soil. Post-fire woody debris constitutes therefore a valuable natural element as a
43 potential source of nutrients, which would be lost from ecosystems in cases where it is
44 removed.

45

46 **Brief summary:**

47 Salvage logging is a widely applied post-fire management that implies the removal of
48 nutrients in the remaining wood. We assess the value of the partially charred wood as a
49 nutrient reservoir for the ecosystem reserves. Wood contributions were particularly
50 relevant for N and micronutrients compared to the soil nutrient stocks.

51

- 52 **Additional keywords:** forest management, Mediterranean mountain, post-fire salvage
- 53 logging, silvicultural treatments, soil nutrients, woody debris, wood nutrients

54 **Introduction**

55 Wildfires exert a strong perturbation to the ecosystem nutrient cycle, leading
56 to an immediate nutrient mobilization from organic pools (Trabaud 1994; Whelan 1995;
57 Page-Dumroese and Jurgensen 2006). Vegetation, litter and soil organic layers are
58 susceptible to be consumed in greater or lesser degrees by fire depending on the
59 temperature reached and their flammability, and according to their specific temperatures
60 of volatilisation, their nutrients are either released to the atmosphere as smoke or
61 deposited to the soil as ash (Iglesias *et al.* 1997; Neary *et al.* 1999; Johnson *et al.* 2005).
62 As a consequence, a fire causes a net decrease in the total nutrient reserves in the
63 ecosystem.

64 The deposited ashes can contribute to increase the soil nutrient availability in
65 the short term (Certini *et al.* 1999, Augusto *et al.* 2007, Pereira *et al.* 2011).
66 Nonetheless, the consequent nutrient enrichment in soil is usually ephemeral in most of
67 the cases, (Iglesias *et al.* 1997; Wan *et al.* 2001; Yang *et al.* 2003, Ferreira *et al.* 2005),
68 as the reduction of stability and nutrient retention capacity of the soil exacerbate the loss
69 of nutrients by leaching and erosion (DeBano *et al.* 1998; Thomas *et al.* 1999, 2000,
70 Certini 2005; Fernández *et al.*, 2007; Shakesby 2011). The existence of a nutrient
71 reservoir in the ecosystem in the long term is, therefore, key to ensure the sustainability
72 of the plant community, especially during the first stages of succession (Jurgensen *et al.*
73 1997; Augusto *et al.* 2000, 2008, Merino *et al.* 2003, 2005).

74 Coarse woody debris may have an important role in both biochemical cycling
75 and ecosystem functioning. During growth, trees incorporate and accumulate nutrients
76 from the soil in the proportions needed to constitute biomass, even where soils are poor
77 (Ingestad 1979; Clarkson and Hanson 1980; Chapin *et al.* 2002). On the other hand,
78 woody material usually represents the largest proportion of biomass in the forest,

79 although this varies according to the characteristics of the stand (tree density, forest
80 species, climate, etc.). Overall, it is estimated that coarse woody tree fractions (stem
81 wood excluding bark and thick branches) represent about 75-90% of the total
82 aboveground biomass of a pine forests (Ouro *et al.* 2001; Merino *et al.* 2003, 2005).
83 Moreover, this estimation ascends to about 95% of the total tree biomass if stumps and
84 roots are also included (Alriksson and Eriksson 1998; Rademacher 2005), while the rest
85 is accounted for by needles, thin branches, twigs, cones and stem bark. Therefore,
86 although the nutrient concentrations in the woody tissues are usually the lowest
87 compared to the rest of the tree fractions, they can contain a high proportion of the
88 nutrients (Alriksson and Eriksson 1998; Ouro *et al.* 2001; Merino *et al.* 2003, 2005;
89 Rademacher 2005) and act as an ecosystem sink and reservoir.

90 The sudden nutrient mobilization and loss provoked during a wildfire and in the
91 immediate period after is restricted mostly to the leaves and fine fractions of vegetation
92 (Trabaud 1994; Johnson *et al.* 2005). However, most of the nutrients contained in the
93 large woody material (trunks and thick branches) and in the roots will likely remain in
94 the ecosystem (Wei *et al.* 1997; Tinker and Knight 2000; Johnson *et al.* 2005), as the
95 temperatures reached inside the first centimetres of the matrix of coarse woody fractions
96 during the heat wave are not high enough to volatilize its components (Czimczik *et al.*
97 2002). In fact, even after intense stand-replacing crown fires, charring is usually limited
98 to the bark or the outer superficial wood layer, remaining unburned most of the standing
99 tree boles (Stocks *et al.* 2004). The nutrients contained in the post-fire coarse woody
100 debris will be progressively released later during the decay process (Brown *et al.* 1996;
101 Wei *et al.* 1997; Ganjegunte *et al.* 2004; Palviainen *et al.* 2010a, 2010b, Marañón-
102 Jiménez and Castro 2012), allowing their retention by the soil and their availability for

103 microorganisms and developing vegetation (Jurgensen *et al.* 1997; Grove and Meggs
104 2003; Brais *et al.* 2005, Marañón-Jiménez and Castro 2012).

105 Ecosystem nutrient losses associated with wildfires have been estimated in
106 several studies (DeBano and Conrad 1978; Wei *et al.* 1997; Thomas *et al.* 1999, 2000,
107 Brais *et al.* 2000; Wan *et al.* 2001; Yang *et al.* 2003, Johnson *et al.* 2005). In this
108 respect, Wei *et al.* (1997) suggested that the nutrients (N and P) contained in pine
109 unburnt stemwood are comparable to the nutrient losses associated with low severity
110 wildfires. Likewise, the contributions of deposited ash after a wildfire for the soil
111 nutrient availability and nutrient cycling in the short term has been remarked by a
112 considerable number of studies (Bramryd and Fransman 1995, Certini *et al.* 1999,
113 Augusto *et al.* 2007, Pereira *et al.* 2011, Johnson *et al.* 2012). However, there is scarce
114 information about the elemental concentrations remaining in charred wood after a
115 wildfire to date, and what is more, the magnitude of the nutrient pools of charred woody
116 material after a wildfire and their potential role in the ecosystem nutrient reserves has
117 not been assessed yet. The estimation of the nutrient reservoir in the post-fire woody
118 debris is however a key first step to assess ecosystem sustainability towards its
119 regeneration. In a previous study, we assessed the long term effects of the presence of
120 the decomposing post-fire wood biomass on soil fertility and soil biogeochemical
121 functioning (Marañón-Jiménez and Castro 2012). In this work, we intend to evaluate the
122 potential biogeochemical relevance, in terms of magnitude, of the nutrient pool in the
123 remaining wood at the starting point, before decomposition and after the short term
124 effects of ash deposition. We analyse the initial macro and micronutrient concentrations
125 in charred pine logs 6 months after the wildfire, and the available nutrients in the soil 2
126 years after the fire. This is done across an altitudinal gradient that varies in climatic
127 conditions and pine species, with the potential to affect soil and wood nutritional status.

128 Nutrient pools in the charred wood are further estimated and compared to the pool of
129 nutrients in the soil to evaluate their relative relevance. The main objectives of this
130 study are to: 1) determine the nutrient concentrations in the charred wood left after a
131 wildfire along the altitudinal gradient, and 2) assess the relative magnitude of the
132 nutrient reservoir in the post-fire wood biomass in relation to the available nutrient
133 stocks in the soil.

134

135 **Material and methods**

136 *Study area*

137 The study site is located in the Sierra Nevada Natural and National Parks (SE
138 Spain; UTM: 456070; 4089811), where in September 2005 the Lanjarón wildfire
139 burned *ca.* 1,300 ha of reforested pine forest between 35 and 45 years old (Fig.1). Fire
140 severity was qualitatively estimated by the visible impacts on the trees and on the
141 different woody fractions, on understorey vegetation and by the colour of deposited
142 ashes just after the wildfire. Fire consumed all the leaves, twigs, litter, understorey
143 vegetation and charred the bark of the trunks. All the trees were killed in the study area
144 and the fire flames reached and consumed the crown of the trees (*ca.* 8 m high). The
145 colour of the deposited ash ranged between clear grey and white. Attending to these
146 indicators, the fire was classified as a high severity crown fire by the Forest Service.

147 The climate is Mediterranean, with rainfall concentrated in spring and autumn,
148 alternating with hot, dry summers. Mean annual precipitation is 470 ± 50 mm, with
149 summer precipitation (June, July and August pooled) of 17 ± 4 mm (1988-2008; climatic
150 data from a meteorological station at 1465 m a.s.l.). Snow falls during winter, usually
151 persisting from November to March above 2000 m a.s.l. The mean annual temperature
152 is $12.3\pm 0.4^\circ\text{C}$ at 1652 m a.s.l. (State Meteorological Agency, period 1994-2008).

153 Ministry of Environment) and $7.8 \pm 0.7^\circ\text{C}$ at 2300 m a.s.l. (data from meteorological
154 station, period 2008-10).

155 The fire-killed pine stands occupy an altitudinal gradient from *ca.* 1300 to 2300
156 m a.s.l (Fig. 1). Across this gradient, we established four study sites of *ca.* 3 ha (sites 1
157 to 4, respectively) that were similar in terms of fire severity (high), situation (southwest
158 exposure), bedrock (micaschists), tree density and tree size (Table 1). The dominant
159 pine species at each site varied according to climatic conditions (Table 1). Between
160 January and March 2006 (4-6 months after the wildfire), the Forest Service felled the
161 trees with the use of manually operated chainsaws, the main branches were lopped off,
162 and all wood was left in situ on the ground. Logs and branches diffusely covered
163 approximately 45% of the surface at ground level (Castro *et al.* 2011). Post-fire
164 vegetation was composed mainly of grasses and forbs with a cover of approximately
165 70% (Castro *et al.* 2010). Dominant species were *Ulex parviflorus*, *Adenocarpus*
166 *decorticans*, *Festuca scariosa*, *Dactylis glomerata* and *Euphorbia flavicoma* in site 1;
167 *Ulex parviflorus*, *Adenocarpus decorticans*, *Festuca scariosa*, *Sangisorba minor* and
168 *Euphorbia flavicoma* in site 2; *Vaccaria hispanica*, *Sesamoides prostrata*, *Senecio*
169 *nebrodensis* and *Helianthemum apenninum* in site 3; and *Genista versicolor*, *Festuca*
170 *spp.*, and *Sesamoides prostrata* in site 4.

171

172 *Wood sampling*

173 During tree felling by the Forest Service (March 2006), discs of 6-8 cm thick
174 were sawed (with a chainsaw) from 50 logs randomly chosen per site and taken to the
175 laboratory. We intentionally delayed the wood sampling until *ca.* 6 months after the
176 fire, once the ash deposited over the charred trunk surfaces have been already lost by the
177 effect of wind and rain (see Appendix A for information about the rain events occurred

178 9 months after the fire), in order to discard the contribution of nutrients that are stored in
179 the ashes but that can be lost at the short term. These discs were considered a
180 representative sample of the initial characteristics of the charred wood, since they
181 showed no signs of decomposition. The disc diameter did not differ among sites and
182 was 12.7 ± 0.3 cm of average. The remaining bark was removed and wood discs were
183 oven-dried at 70°C to constant weight to determine the dry weight. Sawdust samples
184 were taken from the whole section of the disc to maintain proportions of hardwood and
185 softwood in the log, the composition being considered representative of the whole. For
186 this, we used an adapted mechanical saw with no lubricant to avoid contamination. The
187 extracted sawdust (<1 mm) from each disc was collected in paper envelopes and stored
188 in a dry place for later chemical analysis.

189

190 *Wood chemical analyses*

191 The carbon and nitrogen concentrations of sawdust samples were determined
192 using the combustion furnace technique at 850°C (Leco TruSpec autoanalyzer), and
193 phosphorus was analysed using the molybdovanadate method [Association of Official
194 Analytical Chemists (AOAC) 1975]. Meso and micronutrients (Ca, Mg, K, Na, Fe, Mn,
195 Zn and Cu) were determined by atomic absorption of the vegetal ash solution (Métodos
196 Oficiales de Análisis de Plantas 1981) with a Perkin Elmer 5100 spectrometer. The
197 sawdust was dried at 105°C by a thermogravimetric analyser (Leco TGA 701), and
198 nutrient concentrations referred to the corresponding dry weight.

199

200 *Soil sampling*

201 In June 2008 (2 years after the wildfire), 12 soil samples were collected from
202 bare areas without woody debris at each site. By that time, we may assume that the

203 immediate post-fire runoff and lixiviation of nutrients in deposited ashes had occurred
204 (Wan *et al.* 2001; Yang *et al.* 2003, Ferreira *et al.* 2005), and thus this sampling
205 allowed us to characterize soil conditions excluding ephemeral effects of ash deposition
206 (see Appendix A for information about the rain events occurred 2 years after the fire).
207 For each soil sample, three-four soil pits were extracted using a gouge auger (2.5 cm
208 diameter) to 10 cm depth, and homogenized to compound a single soil sample. Samples
209 were immediately sieved at 2 mm and stored to 4°C. Within 24 h of soil sampling, two
210 subsamples of 15 and 7.5 g of soil were extracted for 1 h in agitation with 75 mL of 2
211 M KCl and 0.5 M NaHCO₃, respectively, and filtered through a Whatman GF-D filter.
212 Extracts were frozen at -20°C until analyzed (Schinner *et al.* 1995). A 30 g subsample
213 was oven-dried at 105°C for 48 h for gravimetric determination of water content by the
214 difference between fresh and dry weight, and stored for further analyses. The bulk
215 density is referred to the dry weight and volume of the soil fraction <2 mm. For each
216 soil pit, this volume was calculated as the difference between the volume of the gouge
217 auger to a depth of 10 cm and the volume of the water displaced by the fraction >2 mm
218 (Blake and Hartge 1986).

219

220 *Soil chemical analyses*

221 From the dried subsample, soil organic matter (SOM) content was determined
222 by incineration at 550°C with a thermobalance (Leco TGA 701, St. Joseph, MI, USA) to
223 constant weight (Sparks 1996), whereas total C (C_{tot}) and N (N_{tot}) were determined by
224 combustion at 850°C (Leco TruSpec autoanalyzer). Total inorganic C (TIC) was
225 measured by acidification with HClO₄ in a coulometer (UIC CM-5014, Joliet, IL,
226 USA). The TIC showed mere trace concentrations for these acidic soils
227 (0.0034±0.0012% at site 1 and non detectible at sites 2, 3 and 4), so that C_{tot} can be

228 considered as organic C. The soil pH was determined in 2008 samples by stirring and
229 settling in distilled water with a pHmeter (Crison micropH-2001, Barcelona, Spain),
230 according to the international standard ISO 10390 (1994) (Pansu and Gautheyrou 2006).
231 Ammonium (NH_4^+) and nitrate (NO_3^-) were determined from KCl extracts by the
232 Kjeldahl method (Bremner and Keeney 1965) with a Buchi distillation unit B-324 and a
233 Metrohm SM Titrino 702 titrator. Available inorganic P (P_{inorg}) was determined in
234 NaHCO_3 extracts by the Olsen method (Watanabe and Olsen 1965) with a Perkin Elmer
235 2400 spectrophotometer (Waltham, MA, USA). Meso and micronutrients (Ca, Mg, K,
236 Na, Fe, Mn, Zn and Cu) were determined by cation displacement with ammonium
237 acetate and later analysis by atomic absorption with a Perkin Elmer 5100 spectrometer.
238 The cation exchange capacity (CEC) was obtained after saturation of the soil exchange
239 complex with Na^+ cations by adding sodium acetate, and later determination of the
240 displaced Na^+ cations with ammonium acetate by atomic absorption (Soil Conservation
241 Service 1972). The soil texture was determined by the standard pipette method after
242 Robinson-Köhn or Andreasen (Pansu and Gautheyrou 2006). Soil mineralogy was
243 determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) after milling a soil subsample to powder
244 (Whittig and Allardice 1986) with an X-ray diffractometer (Bruker D8 Advance,
245 Madrid, Spain). All nutrient fractions were referred to the corresponding dry weight of
246 the soil.

247

248 *Nutrient pools estimation*

249 The biogeochemical relevance of the remaining post-fire wood biomass was
250 assessed by comparing both the soil and wood pools of nutrients as a result of the
251 wildfire. In order to estimate the nutrient content of the charred wood, we calculated the
252 dry wood biomass using specific equations developed by Montero *et al.* (2006) and

253 implemented by the INIA in the calculation tool cubiFOR (CeseFor, url:
254 <http://cubifor.cesefor.com/>). For each experimental site, the means of dasometric
255 variables (tree density, d.b.h and tree height; table 1) were introduced to specific
256 equations according to the dominant pine species. The fraction of needles and twigs <2
257 cm were not considered, since these fractions were consumed during the wildfire. The
258 resultant values of total aboveground biomass per area and the wood nutrient
259 concentrations (Table 2) allowed the estimation of the nutrient content per area of the
260 wood pool for each site.

261 The nutrient content in the upper 10 cm soil layer was calculated using the bulk
262 density for each site (Table 3) and the nutrient concentrations in the soil (Table 4). The
263 N in the soil pool was referred to the extractable inorganic fraction ($\text{NH}_4^+ + \text{NO}_3^-$), since
264 it is broadly accepted that this is the most relevant direct N source for plant nutrition in
265 most of the cases (Killham 1994), whereas direct evidence that organic N contributes
266 significantly to plant N nutrition is still lacking (Näsholm *et al.* 2009).

267

268 *Data analysis*

269 The differences in nutrient concentrations in wood and soil were analyzed with
270 one-way analysis of variances (ANOVAs), with site as the independent factor. The
271 comparison of mean nutrient concentrations between sites was further analyzed with
272 Tukey HSD post-hoc tests. Differences in textures and mineralogy between sites were
273 similarly analyzed using a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test, and, in cases of
274 significant differences, Nemenyi post-hoc tests of multiple comparisons of means
275 among sites were performed (Zar 2010). Additionally, correlations between all nutrients
276 were explored separately for the wood and for the soil using Pearson product-moment
277 correlations. The correlation between the mean concentration per site of each nutrient in

278 the soil and in the wood was also explored by the same method. A principal component
279 analysis (PCA) was also performed for nutrients in wood and soil. For this, a correlation
280 matrix with standardization of variables was used. Further, differences between
281 experimental sites according to the first component scores obtained in the PCA were
282 tested with a one-way ANOVA and Tukey HSD post-hoc tests (Jolliffe 2002; Quinn
283 and Keough 2009).

284 Data were previously log- or square-root-transformed when required before the
285 implementation of parametric statistical analyses (ANOVA's, Pearson's correlations
286 and PCA) to improve normality and homocedasticity (Quinn and Keough 2009).

287 Statistical analyses and models were made with JMP 7.0 software (SAS Institute). In the
288 results that follow, mean values are followed by ± 1 SE.

289

290 **Results:**

291

292 *Wood nutrient concentrations*

293 All nutrient concentrations in wood differed between sites, except Zn and C
294 (Table 2). N was more concentrated in sites 2 and 3, so that the ratio C:N in the wood
295 was lower in these sites (Table 2). The concentrations of P, Ca and Mg resulted the
296 lowest in site 4. The patterns of K, Na and Fe were similar, becoming also lower as
297 altitude increased (Table 2). However, the Mn concentration had again the opposite
298 pattern, increasing at higher elevations (Table 2). Cu was lower in sites 1 and 4, and
299 highest in site 2 (Table 2).

300 Strong correlations were found between the N, P and the majority-components
301 of the wood Ca, Mg and K being positive in all cases (Appendix B). These were
302 especially important between K and P, Na or Mg ($r=0.75$, 0.59 and 0.54 respectively,

303 P<0.0001 in all cases) and between P and Na ($r=0.51$, $P<0.0001$, Appendix B). High
304 positive correlations were also found between Mg and Ca, Na or P ($r>0.36$, $P<0.0001$),
305 and between Fe and Cu or Zn ($r>0.33$, $P<0.0001$). Additionally, Mn was inversely
306 correlated to K ($r=-0.39$, $P<0.0001$, Appendix B).

307 The study sites showed some gradual differences according to the principal
308 components of the wood composition. The first and second principal components
309 obtained in the PCA explained the 29.6% and 16.1% of the total variance, respectively
310 (Fig. 2A and B). K, P and Mg contributed more to the first component and Zn, C and N
311 to the second (Fig. 2A). According to the first component, the site 4 had the lowest
312 scores, and thus, the lowest concentrations of K, P, Mg and highest of Mn. This site was
313 followed by site 3 and then sites 1 and 2, being the latter two no significantly different
314 between them (one-way ANOVA; $P<0.0001$; Fig. 2A and B).

315

316 *Soil parameters and nutrient concentrations*

317 Experimental sites had lower pH values with increasing altitude, whereas SOM
318 and CEC were the highest at the most elevated site (Table 3). Soil nutrient
319 concentrations differed significantly between experimental sites in the case of C_{tot} , N_{tot} ,
320 P_{inorg} , Ca, Mg and Mn (Table 4). C_{tot} and N_{tot} showed the same pattern as SOM, being
321 highest at the most elevated site, with the same tendency for NO_3^- (Tables 3 and 4). The
322 C:N ratio in soil was higher in sites 1 and 2 and lowest in site 3 (Table 4). Most of the N
323 in the soil was organic and only *ca.* 0.54% was inorganic. The P_{inorg} was lower in site 2
324 and higher in site 4 (Table 4). The exchangeable Ca and Mg had similar patterns
325 between experimental sites, being higher in sites 1 and 2 (Table 4). Despite the absence
326 of significant differences, Fe, Cu and Zn tended to be lowest at the most elevated site.
327 Mn had an opposite pattern, increasing with the elevation (Table 4).

328 The pH, SOM, CEC, C_{tot} and N_{tot} , P_{inorg} and Mn were strongly correlated
329 (Appendix C). For the pH, these correlations are negative ($r < -0.35$, $P < 0.001$ in all cases,
330 Appendix C). Ca, Mg and pH presented also very high correlations, although for these
331 nutrients the relationship with pH was positive ($r > 0.40$, $P < 0.001$ in all cases, Appendix
332 C). Also meaningful are the correlations between NO_3^- and NH_4^+ ($r = 0.75$, $P < 0.0001$),
333 Fe and Cu ($r = 0.59$, $P < 0.0001$), and between K and C_{tot} or P_{inorg} ($r > 0.39$, $P < 0.001$ in all
334 cases, Appendix C).

335 Some of the study sites can be even more clearly differentiated by their soil
336 nutrients and edaphic parameters than by the wood nutrients, according to the principal
337 components obtained in the PCA (Fig. 2C and D). The first and second principal
338 components explain a 30.9% and 16.9% of the total variance (Fig. 2C and D). The
339 concentrations of N, C, SOM and pH contributed more to the first component, whereas
340 Ca and Mg were the variables that contributed more to the second component (Fig. 2C).
341 According to the first component, the site 4 had the highest scores, and therefore, the
342 highest concentrations of N, C, SOM and lowest pH. It is followed by the site 3, and
343 then sites 1 and 2, without significant differences between these latter two ($P < 0.0001$;
344 one-way ANOVA; Fig. 2C and D).

345 In addition, correlations between the concentration of each nutrient obtained in
346 the soil and in the wood were significant in the case of the Mn ($r = 0.99$, $P = 0.0078$) and
347 the Zn ($r = 0.92$, $P = 0.0787$).

348

349 **Discussion:**

350 The results of this study highlight the potential of post-fire wood biomass as a
351 nutrient source for natural forest regeneration. Two years after the wildfire, soils in the
352 study area showed low nutrient availability, although they varied among the study sites
353 likely due to differences of mineralogy and microclimate. On the other hand, the

354 relative potential contributions of the wood pool were very relevant, due to the low soil
355 nutrient availability, the concentrations of these elements still present in the wood after
356 the fire, and the high biomass of charred wood remaining. Moreover, the relative
357 relevance of the post-fire wood biomass as a reservoir of nutrients for the ecosystem
358 was quite consistent across study sites, regardless of the differences in soil and wood
359 nutrient concentrations, soil characteristics and wood biomass remaining after the
360 wildfire.

361

362 *Soil nutrient concentrations*

363 Overall, soil nutrient concentrations in this study were lower than those reported
364 for other soils in the area (Sánchez-Marañón *et al.* 1996) and in other Mediterranean
365 pine forests (De Marco *et al.* 2005; Fierro *et al.* 2007; Blanco *et al.* 2008; Yilziz *et al.*
366 2010). This may be due to several reasons such as the nutrient losses associated to the
367 organic layer combustion by the wildfire (DeBano and Conrand 1978; Raison 1979;
368 Certini 2005) and the recurrent history of degradative land use in the area (Padilla *et al.*
369 2010). The pre-fire existence of a pine forest with a litter input of high C:N ratio and
370 difficult mineralization could also have contributed to soil acidification and low nutrient
371 availability (van Wesemael 1993; Moro and Domingo 2000; Oyonarte *et al.* 2008),
372 particularly in the case of the inorganic forms of N for plant assimilation. The low pool
373 of nutrients found in the soil are likely insufficient to meet the annual requirements of
374 available inorganic N (*ca.* 40 kg ha⁻¹year⁻¹), K (*ca.* 25 kg ha⁻¹year⁻¹), Zn (*ca.* 0.14 kg ha⁻¹
375 year⁻¹), Fe (*ca.* 0.18 kg ha⁻¹year⁻¹), and to a lesser degree, of P (*ca.* 4 kg ha⁻¹year⁻¹) and
376 Mn (*ca.* 0.85 kg ha⁻¹year⁻¹) of a mature coniferous forest. However, despite their low
377 concentrations in this siliceous soil, Ca and Mg were not limiting (Cole and Rapp 1981;
378 Miller 1986; Johnson and Lindberg 1992; Helmisaari 1995; Merino *et al.* 2005).

379 Among sites, available or changeable soil nutrients were modulated by
380 differences in pH and SOM, as a result of the different lithology and microclimate, and
381 to a lesser degree by weathering of the parent material and soil development. As altitude
382 increase, temperatures are lower and the lithology becomes more acidic. These factors
383 explain the lower pH found at highest altitudes and the highest SOM, provided the
384 slower mineralization and prevalence of humification processes (Bohn *et al.* 1993;
385 Silver 1998). The higher SOM determined, in turn, a higher CEC, total C and N at the
386 highest site. Furthermore, the $N_{\text{inorg}}:N_{\text{total}}$ ratio was also consistent with the greater
387 predominance of humification. The contrasting effects of the decrease in pH and the
388 highest CEC at the most elevated site explain the decreasing pattern of the base
389 saturation with altitude (Porta *et al.* 2003). Similarly, CEC and pH also modulate the
390 pattern of available inorganic P. Phosphorous become insoluble at medium-high pH,
391 leading to precipitation mainly with Ca, Mg and Fe. Consequently, phosphorous
392 concentrations were highest at the most elevated site due to the highest solubility of
393 phosphates at acid pH and the higher retention capacity of the soil (Porta *et al.* 2003).
394 By contrast, the acidity increases the Mn solubility and availability (Godo and
395 Reisenauer 1980), and reinforces the retention of NO_3^- anions by the protoned surfaces
396 of colloids (Ashman and Puri 2002). In addition, the tendencies of lower Cu, Fe and Zn
397 availability at the highest site are likely due to lesser release from a not very weathered
398 parent material. The young nature of these soils is in fact evidenced by the greater
399 presence of easily weatherable chlorite minerals at this site (Thompson and Troeh 2005).

400

401 *Wood nutrient concentrations*

402 The essential nutrients found in charred stemwood are within the range of the
403 concentrations reported in other studies for unburnt pine wood for most of the nutrients

404 analyzed. Nonetheless, the mean concentrations of N in pine wood found in this study
405 (0.17%, all sites pooled) exceed the range of values reported in the literature for the
406 same species (0.05-0.15%; Alriksson and Eriksson 1998; Augusto *et al.* 2000, 2008;
407 Merino *et al.* 2005; Palviainen *et al.* 2010a). The P concentrations here averaged 89.2
408 ppm versus the values of 45-180 ppm in other studies. Similarly, Ca, Mg and K
409 averaged here 605.47 ppm, 238.35 ppm and 413.36 ppm, respectively, versus the ranges
410 of 500-1100 ppm, 100-300 ppm and 250-1000 ppm found for the same elements in the
411 literature (Alriksson and Eriksson 1998; Augusto *et al.* 2000, 2008; Merino *et al.* 2005;
412 Palviainen *et al.* 2010b). Nutrient concentrations present in the large wood fractions are
413 therefore still relatively high in comparison with unburnt wood, likely due to the fact
414 that the effects of fire are usually limited to the bark and small fractions of the tree, even
415 in intense stand-replacing fires (Wei *et al.* 1997; Stocks *et al.* 2004).

416 However, the concentrations of Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu and Na were very low compared
417 to those found in unburnt wood (Harju *et al.* 1997; Alriksson and Eriksson 1998;
418 Saarela *et al.* 2002; Merino *et al.* 2005). This could be likely due to their limited
419 availability in soil (see above). This is also supported by the similar patterns of Mn, Zn
420 and Cu both in the wood and in the soil across sites, and by the correlations found
421 between the concentrations in wood and soil in the case of Mn and Zn. The same thing
422 occurred between the N in wood and NH_4^+ in soil, suggesting a limitation of a source of
423 available N in the soil. Thus, nutrients in wood tended to reflect their availability in the
424 soil, being therefore lower at the most elevated sites, although others factors like the
425 differences in composition among the dominant pine species could be also influencing
426 (Alriksson and Eriksson 1998; Augusto *et al.* 2000, 2008; Baumann *et al.* 2006).

427

428 *Relative magnitude of the nutrient reservoir in post-fire woody debris*

429 During a high-severity wildfire, nutrients contained in fine nutrient-rich vegetal
430 fractions, such as leaves and twigs, are mostly volatilized (Trabaud 1994; Johnson *et al.*
431 2005). However, our results show that a relatively high nutrient concentration was still
432 present in charred wood and that great amounts of biomass remained after the wildfire.
433 Figure 3 shows the nutrient reservoir contained in soil and aboveground charred wood
434 biomass and the ratio among these two components. The magnitude of the nutrient
435 pools in the post-fire remaining wood was very relevant from a biochemical
436 perspective. As an example, the estimated N and P reservoirs represented by charred
437 wood remaining (49.9 kg ha^{-1} and 2.6 kg ha^{-1} , Fig. 3) would be comparable to the inputs
438 of atmospheric deposition for this area during 8 and 13 years, respectively (6.3 kg ha^{-1}
439 year^{-1} of N and $0.2 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{year}^{-1}$ of P; Morales-Baquero *et al.* 2006). Similarly, the N in
440 the wood pool would be the equivalent to the estimated N input by fixation of *ca.* 1800
441 *Adenocarpus decorticans* per ha in a similar Mediterranean ecosystem during at least 50
442 years ($1 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}\text{year}^{-1}$ of N; Moro *et al.* 1996). Moreover, the magnitude of the nutrient
443 reservoir in post-fire wood pool is likely even greater than that estimated, as the nutrient
444 concentrations of branches (11% of the total aboveground biomass) are usually higher
445 than those of stemwood (Alriksson and Eriksson 1998; Montero *et al.* 1999). In
446 addition, we are not taking into account the nutrient reservoir in belowground biomass
447 (estimated as a 34% of the total biomass for this study site) or the nutrient contributions
448 by deposited ashes.

449 The relative contribution of the wood in relation to the soil pool was especially
450 high in the case of N, Na, Mn, Fe, Zn and Cu, reaching wood:soil ratios up to 9 for N
451 and from 2 to 5 in the case of the micronutrients (Fig. 3). The partially charred wood
452 will therefore be especially suitable, helping to satisfy the requirements of these
453 nutrients that were found insufficient in the soil. Moreover, the important contribution

454 of micronutrients in charred wood biomass represents a sign of their suitable potential
455 as a nutrient reservoir. Trees incorporate and concentrate these micronutrients in their
456 biomass although they were very limited in the soil (Ingestad 1979; Clarkson and
457 Hanson 1980; Chapin *et al.* 2002). As a result, a much greater total amount of these
458 nutrients was contained in wood than in the first 10 cm of soil. In addition, overall the
459 relative contributions of charred wood remained quite constant among study sites and
460 were independent of the different microclimate, mineralogy, pre-fire dominant species
461 and wood biomass inventory. Nonetheless, we are aware of possible underestimation of
462 the soil nutrients pools, since it is referred to the upper 10 cm soil layer. However,
463 limiting nutrients for plants are mostly concentrated in the upper mineral layers
464 (Jobbágy and Jackson 2001), so the relative contributions of each pool are not expected
465 to vary substantially. Summarizing, the results of this study show that the remains of
466 partially charred wood biomass act as a relevant nutrient reservoir, which will provide a
467 source of nutrients in the long term (Marañón-Jiménez and Castro 2012) and help to
468 mitigate the nutrient losses associated with the wildfire and post-fire management.

469

470 *Management implications*

471 The prior forest conditions (tree density, tree diameter and age class, degree of
472 management, nutritional status, etc.), fire severity and the post-fire intervention will
473 radically determine the magnitudes of nutrient pools in the charred wood after a
474 wildfire. In spite of that, the appropriate management of charred woody material
475 remains controversial (McIver and Starr 2001; Beschta *et al.* 2004; Lindenmayer *et al.*
476 2004, 2008; Donato *et al.* 2006). Results in this study can assist to implement post-fire
477 measures designed to ensure the regeneration and natural sustainability of the
478 ecosystem. Salvage logging (felling and removing charred trunks, often combined with

479 the elimination of the remaining woody debris; McIver and Starr 2001; Beschta *et al.*
480 2004) is a widely applied management practise in forest ecosystems all over the world.
481 This implies the retrieval of the nutrient pool contained in aboveground woody debris
482 that could otherwise be reincorporated to the ecosystem biogeochemical cycle.
483 Moreover, post-fire salvage logging represents in these cases an additional perturbation
484 beyond the wildfire that usually exceeds the resilience and adaptation capacity of the
485 ecosystem (Paine *et al.* 1998; Lindenmayer *et al.* 2008). The elimination of the potential
486 nutrient incomes can hinder soil biogeochemical functioning (Marañón-Jiménez and
487 Castro 2012), microbial mineralization (Marañón-Jiménez *et al.* 2011) and vegetation
488 productivity (Castro *et al.* 2011), thus retarding the capacity of such ecosystem to
489 restore its carbon sink capacity (Serrano-Ortiz *et al.* 2011). For this reason, the
490 biochemical impacts of salvage logging should be also added to the considerations to be
491 evaluated during the decision-making regarding the most suitable post-fire forest
492 management strategy.

493

494 **Conclusions:**

495 The partially charred wood remaining after a forest fire still contains great
496 amounts of nutrients, which represent a valuable reservoir as well as a potential source
497 for the regenerating ecosystem in the longer term. In this study, the magnitude of these
498 stocks was especially prominent in the case of N and the micronutrients Na, Mn, Fe, Zn
499 and Cu, where stocks in the burnt wood were higher than those existing in the upper 10
500 cm soil layer. Moreover, the relevance of wood as a potential nutrient source coincided
501 with those nutrients that were deficient to satisfy the requirements of a mature forest.
502 Therefore, the suitability of the remaining woody debris after fires for the nutrient
503 capital of the ecosystem should be considered for post-fire management of burnt areas.

504

505 **Acknowledgements:**

506 We wish to thank Ramón Ruíz Puche and Enrique P. Sánchez-Cañete for their hard
 507 work in the field, Gustavo Román Reche for his assistance in processing the wood
 508 samples, Susana Hitos for her invaluable help and advice in the laboratory analyses,
 509 Francisco Martín Peinado for his help and collaboration with the soil texture and
 510 mineralogical analyses, and Ivan Janssens for his inestimably useful comments. The
 511 *Consejería de Medio Ambiente (Junta de Andalucía)* and the *Parque Nacional y*
 512 *Natural de Sierra Nevada* offered support in establishing the treatments. This work was
 513 financed by the by the projects (SUM2006-00010-00-00) of the *INIA*, (10/2005) of the
 514 *Organismo Autónomo de Parques Nacionales (MMA)*, *GESBOME* (P06-RNM-1890) of
 515 the *Junta de Andalucía*, *COILEX* (CGL2008-01671), *CARBORED-II* (CGL2010-22193-
 516 C04-02) and Subprogram for Technical Support (PTA2009-1782-I) of the *MICINN*, and
 517 by a grant *FPU-MEC* to S.M.J.

518

519 **References:**

520 Alriksson A, Eriksson HM (1998) Variations in mineral nutrient and C distribution in
 521 the soil and vegetation compartments of five temperate tree species in NE
 522 Sweden. *Forest Ecology and Management* **108**, 261-273.

523 Ashman MR, Puri G (Eds) (2002) 'Essential of Soil Science'. (Blackwell Publishing:
 524 Oxford).

525 Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC) (Eds) (1975) Methods of
 526 Analysis. (AOAC: Washington DC).

- 527 Augusto L, Bakker MR, Meredieu C (2007) Wood ash applications to temperate forest
528 ecosystems - potential benefits and drawbacks. In 'Zinc Crops 2007 Conference',
529 May 24-26 2007, Istanbul, TURKEY, pp. 181-198.
- 530 Augusto L, Meredieu C, Bert D, Trichet P, Porte A, Bosc A, Lagane F, Loustau D,
531 Pellerin S, Danjon F, Ranger J, Gelpe J (2008) Improving models of forest
532 nutrient export with equations that predict the nutrient concentration of tree
533 compartments. *Annals of Forest Science* **65**, 1-14.
- 534 Augusto L, Ranger J, Ponette Q, Rapp M (2000) Relationships between forest tree
535 species, stand production and stand nutrient amount. *Annals of Forest Science*
536 **57**, 313-324.
- 537 Baumann K, Rumpelt A, Schneider BU, Marschner P, Huttl RF (2006) Seedling
538 biomass and element content of *Pinus sylvestris* and *Pinus nigra* grown in sandy
539 substrates with lignite. *Geoderma* **136**, 573-578.
- 540 Beschta RL, Rhodes JJ, Kauffman JB, Griesswell RE, Minshall GW, Karr JR, Perry
541 DA, Hauer ER, Frissell CA (2004) Postfire management on forested public lands
542 of the western United States. *Conservation Biology* **18**, 957-967.
- 543 Blake GR, Hartge KH (1986) Bulk density. In 'Methods of soil analysis. Part 1.
544 Physical and mineralogical methods. SSSA Monograph No. 9'. (Ed A Klute) pp.
545 363-375. (ASA: Madison)
- 546 Blanco JA, Imbert JB, Castillo FJ (2008) Nutrient return via litterfall in two contrasting
547 *Pinus sylvestris* forests in the Pyrenees under different thinning intensities.
548 *Forest Ecology and Management* **256**, 1840-1852.
- 549 Bohn HL, McNeal BL, O'Connor GA (Eds) (1993) 'Soil chemistry'. (John Wiley &
550 Sons: New York)

- 551 Brais S, David P, Ouimet R (2000) Impacts of wild fire severity and salvage harvesting
552 on the nutrient balance of jack pine and black spruce boreal stands. *Forest*
553 *Ecology and Management* **137**, 231-243.
- 554 Brais S, Sadi R, Bergeron Y, Grenier Y (2005) Coarse woody debris dynamics in a
555 post-fire jack pine chronosequence and its relation with site productivity. *Forest*
556 *Ecology and Management* **220**, 216-226.
- 557 Bramryd T, Fransman B (1995) Silvicultural use of wood ashes — Effects on the
558 nutrient and heavy metal balance in a pine (*Pinus sylvestris*, L) forest soil.
559 *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution* **85**, 1039-1044.
- 560 Bremner JM, Keeney DR (1965) Steam distillation methods for determination of
561 ammonium, nitrate and nitrite. *Analytica Chimica Acta* **32**, 485-495
- 562 Brown S, Mo JM, McPherson JK, Bell DT (1996) Decomposition of woody debris in
563 Western Australian forests. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research-Revue*
564 *Canadienne De Recherche Forestiere* **26**, 954-966.
- 565 Castro J, Allen CD, Molina-Morales M, Marañón-Jiménez S, Sánchez-Miranda A,
566 Zamora R (2011) Salvage logging versus the use of burnt wood as a nurse object
567 to promote post-fire tree seedling establishment. *Restoration Ecology* **19**, 537-
568 544.
- 569 Castro J, Marañón-Jiménez S, Sánchez-Miranda A, Lorite J (2010) Efecto del manejo
570 de la madera quemada sobre la regeneración forestal post-incendio: Desarrollo
571 de técnicas blandas de restauración ecológica. In 'Proyectos de investigación en
572 parques nacionales: 2006-2009' (Eds. L Ramírez, B Asensio) pp. 139-157.
573 (Organismo Autónomo de Parques Nacionales: Madrid)
- 574 Certini G (2005) Effects of fire on properties of forest soils: A review. *Oecologia* **143**,
575 1-10.

- 576 Chapin III FS, Matson PA, Mooney HA (Eds) (2002) 'Principles of terrestrial
577 ecosystem ecology'. (Springer: Nueva York)
- 578 Clarkson DT, Hanson JB (1980). The mineral nutrition of higher plants. *Annual Review*
579 *of Plant Physiology* **31**, 239-298
- 580 Cole DW, Rapp M (1981) Elemental cycling in forest ecosystems. In 'Forest soil
581 relationships in North America'. (Ed DE Reichle) pp: 341- 409. (Cambridge
582 University Press: London)
- 583 Czimeczik CI, Preston CM, Schmidt MWI, Werner RA, Schulze ED (2002) Effects of
584 charring on mass, organic carbon, and stable carbon isotope composition of
585 wood. *Organic Geochemistry* **33**, 1207-1223.
- 586 De Marco A, Gentile AE, Arena C, De Santo AV (2005) Organic matter, nutrient
587 content and biological activity in burned and unburned soils of a Mediterranean
588 maquis area of southern Italy. *International Journal of Wildland Fire* **14**, 365-
589 377.
- 590 DeBano LF, Conrad CE (1978) Effect of Fire on Nutrients in a Chaparral Ecosystem.
591 *Ecology* **59**, 489-497.
- 592 DeBano LF, Neary DG, Ffolliott PF (Eds) (1998) 'Fire's Effects on Ecosystems.' (John
593 Wiley and Sons: New York)
- 594 Delgado Calvo-Flores G, Sánchez Marañón M, Párraga Martínez JF, Martín García JM,
595 García Corral PA, Soriano Rodríguez M, Delgado Calvo-Flores R (1993) Mapa
596 de suelos de Lanjarón escala 1:100.000. Proyecto LUCDEME. Ministerio de
597 Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, ICONA, Departamento de Edafología y
598 Química Agrícola de la Universidad de Granada. (Publicaciones del Instituto
599 Nacional para la Conservación de la Naturaleza: Madrid)

- 600 Donato DC, Fontaine JB, Campbell JL, Robinson WD, Kauffman JB, Law BE (2006)
601 Post-wildfire logging hinders regeneration and increases fire risk. *Science* **311**,
602 352-352.
- 603 Fernández C, Vega JA, Fonturbel T, Perez-Gorostiaga P, Jimenez E, Madrigal J (2007)
604 Effects of wildfire, salvage logging and slash treatments on soil degradation.
605 *Land Degradation & Development* **18**, 591-607.
- 606 Ferreira AJD, Coelho COA, Boulet AK, Lopes FP (2005) Temporal patterns of solute
607 loss following wildfires in Central Portugal. *International Journal of Wildland*
608 *Fire* **14**, 401-412.
- 609 Fierro A, Rutigliano FA, De Marco A, Castaldi S, De Santo AV (2007) Post-fire
610 stimulation of soil biogenic emission of CO₂ in a sandy soil of a Mediterranean
611 shrubland. *International Journal of Wildland Fire* **16**, 573-583.
- 612 Ganjgunte GK, Condrona LM, Clintonb PW, Davisb MR, Mahieuc N (2004)
613 Decomposition and nutrient release from radiata pine (*Pinus radiata*) coarse
614 woody debris. *Forest Ecology and Management* **187**, 197-211.
- 615 Godo GH, Reisenauer HM (1980) Plant effects on soil manganese availability. *Soil*
616 *Sciences Society of American Journal* **44**, 993-995.
- 617 Grove SJ, Meggs J (2003) Coarse woody debris, biodiversity and management: A
618 review with particular reference to Tasmanian wet eucalypt forests. *Australian*
619 *Forestry* **66**, 258-272.
- 620 Harju L, Lill J-O, Saarela K-E, Heselius S-J, Hernberg FJ, Lindroos A (1997) Analysis
621 of trace elements in trunk wood by thick-target PIXE using dry ashing for
622 preconcentration. *Fresenius' Journal of Analytical Chemistry* **358**, 523-528.
- 623 Helmisaari H-S (1995) Nutrient cycling in *Pinus sylvestris* stands in eastern Finland.
624 *Plant and Soil* **168-169**, 327-336.

- 625 Iglesias T, Cala V, Gonzalez J (1997) Mineralogical and chemical modifications in soils
626 affected by a forest fire in the Mediterranean area. *Science of the Total*
627 *Environment* **204**, 89-96.
- 628 Ingestad T (1979). Mineral nutrient requirements of *Pinus sylvestris* and *Picea abies*
629 seedlings. *Physiologica plantarum* **45**, 373-380
- 630 Jobbágy EG, Jackson RB (2001) The distribution of soil nutrients with depth: Global
631 patterns and the imprint of plants. *Biogeochemistry* **53**, 51-77.
- 632 Johnson BG, Johnson DW, Miller WW, Board DI (2012) The Effects of Ash Influx on
633 Burned and Unburned Soil Water-Extractable Nutrients Using a Mechanical
634 Vacuum Extractor. *Soil Science* **177**, 338-344.
- 635 Johnson DW, Lindberg SE (Eds) (1992) 'Atmospheric deposition and forest nutrient
636 cycling.' (Springer Verlag: Berlin)
- 637 Johnson DW, Murphy JF, Susfalk RB, Caldwell TG, Miller WW, Walker RF, Powers
638 RF (2005) The effects of wildfire, salvage logging, and post-fire N-fixation on
639 the nutrient budgets of a Sierran forest. *Forest Ecology and Management* **220**,
640 155-165.
- 641 Jolliffe IT (Ed) (2002) 'Principal Components Analysis'. (Springer Series in Statistics,
642 Springer: New York)
- 643 Jurgensen MF, Harvey AE, Graham RT, Page-Dumroese DS, Tonn JR, Larsen MJ, Jain
644 TB (1997) Impacts of timber harvesting on soil organic matter, nitrogen,
645 productivity, and health of Inland Northwest forests. *Forest Science* **43**, 234-
646 251.
- 647 Killham K (Ed) (1994) 'Soil Ecology' (Cambridge University Press: Cambridge)
- 648 Lindenmayer DB, Burton PJ, Franklin JF (Eds) (2008) 'Salvage logging and its
649 ecological consequences'. (Island Press: Washington)

- 650 Lindenmayer DB, Foster DR, Franklin JF, Hunter ML, Noss RF, Schmiegelow FA,
651 Perry D (2004) Salvage harvesting policies after natural disturbance. *Science*
652 **303**, 1303.
- 653 Marañón-Jiménez S, Castro J (2012) Effect of decomposing post-fire coarse woody
654 debris on soil fertility and nutrient availability in a Mediterranean ecosystem.
655 *Biogeochemistry*, 1-17. DOI 10.1007/s10533-012-9744-x
- 656 Marañón-Jiménez S, Castro J, Kowalski AS, Serrano-Ortiz P, Reverter BR, Sánchez-
657 Cañete EP, Zamora R (2011) Post-fire soil respiration in relation to burnt wood
658 management in a Mediterranean mountain ecosystem. *Forest Ecology and*
659 *Management* **261**, 1436-1447.
- 660 McIver JD, Starr L (2001) A literature review on the environmental effects of postfire
661 logging. *Western Journal of Applied Forestry* **16**, 159-168.
- 662 Merino A, Balboa MA, Soalleiro RR, Gonzalez JGA (2005) Nutrient exports under
663 different harvesting regimes in fast-growing forest plantations in southern
664 Europe. *Forest Ecology and Management* **207**, 325-339.
- 665 Merino A, Rey C, Brañas J, Soalleiro RR (2003) Biomasa arbórea y acumulación de
666 nutrientes en plantaciones de *Pinus radiata* D. Don en Galicia. *Investigación*
667 *Agraria: Sistemas y Recursos Forestales* **12**, 85-98.
- 668 Métodos Oficiales de Análisis de Suelos y Aguas, Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca.
669 Orden de 17 de septiembre de 1981.
- 670 Miller HG (1986) Carbon x nutrient interactions - the limitations to productivity. *Tree*
671 *Physiology* **2**, 373-385.
- 672 Montero G, Ruiz-Peinado R, Muñoz M (Eds) (2006) 'Producción de biomasa y fijación
673 de CO₂ por los Bosques Españoles'. (Monografías Instituto Nacional de
674 Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria: Madrid)

- 675 Montero G, Ortega C, Cañellas I, Bachiller A (1999) Productividad aérea y dinámica de
676 nutrientes en una repoblación de *Pinus pinaster* Ait. sometida a distintos
677 regímenes de claras. *Investigación agraria: Sistemas y Recursos Forestales*.
678 **Fuera de Serie nº 1**, 175-206
- 679 Morales-Baquero R, Pulido-Villena E, Reche I (2006) Atmospheric inputs of
680 phosphorus and nitrogen to the southwest Mediterranean region:
681 Biogeochemical responses of high mountain lakes. *Limnology and*
682 *Oceanography* **51**, 830-837.
- 683 Moro MJ, Domingo F (2000) Litter decomposition in four woody species in a
684 Mediterranean climate: Weight loss, N and P dynamics. *Annals of Botany* **86**,
685 1065-1071.
- 686 Moro MJ, Domingo F, Escarre A (1996) Organic matter and nitrogen cycles in a pine
687 afforested catchment with a shrub layer of *Adenocarpus decorticans* and *Cistus*
688 *laurifolius* in south-eastern Spain. *Annals of Botany* **78**, 675-685.
- 689 Näsholm T, Kielland K, Ganeteg U (2009) Uptake of organic nitrogen by plants. *New*
690 *Phytologist* **182**, 31-48.
- 691 Neary DG, Klopatek CC, DeBano LF, Ffolliott PF (1999) Fire effects on belowground
692 sustainability: A review and synthesis. *Forest Ecology and Management* **122**,
693 51-71.
- 694 Ouro G, Pérez-Batallón P, Merino A (2001) Effects of silvicultural practices on
695 nutrient status in a *Pinus radiata* plantation: Nutrient export by tree removal and
696 nutrient dynamics in decomposing logging residues. *Annals of Forest Science*
697 **58**, 411-422.

- 698 Oyonarte C, Aranda V, Durante P (2008) Soil surface properties in Mediterranean
699 mountain ecosystems: Effects of environmental factors and implications of
700 management. *Forest Ecology and Management* **254**, 156-165.
- 701 Padilla FM, Vidal B, Sánchez J, Pugnaire FI (2010) Land-use changes and carbon
702 sequestration through the twentieth century in a Mediterranean mountain
703 ecosystem: Implications for land management. *Journal of Environmental*
704 *Management* **91**, 2688-2695.
- 705 Page-Dumroese DS, Jurgensen MF (2006) Soil carbon and nitrogen pools in mid- to
706 late-successional forest stands of the northwestern United States: Potential
707 impact of fire. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research-Revue Canadienne De*
708 *Recherche Forestiere* **36**, 2270-2284.
- 709 Paine RT, Tegner MJ, Johnson EA (1998) Compounded Perturbations Yield Ecological
710 Surprises. *Ecosystems* **1**, 535-545.
- 711 Palviainen M, Finer L, Laiho R, Shorohova E, Kapitsa E, Vanha-Majamaa I (2010a)
712 Carbon and nitrogen release from decomposing Scots pine, Norway spruce and
713 silver birch stumps. *Forest Ecology and Management* **259**, 390-398.
- 714 Palviainen M, Finer L, Laiho R, Shorohova E, Kapitsa E, Vanha-Majamaa I (2010b)
715 Phosphorus and base cation accumulation and release patterns in decomposing
716 Scots pine, Norway spruce and silver birch stumps. *Forest Ecology and*
717 *Management* **260**, 1478-1489.
- 718 Pansu M, Gautheyrou J (Eds) (2006) 'Handbook of soil analysis. Mineralogical, organic
719 and inorganic methods'. (Springer: Montpellier)
- 720 Pereira P, Úbeda X, Martín D, Mataix-Solera J, Guerrero C (2011) Effects of a low
721 severity prescribed fire on water-soluble elements in ash from a cork oak

- 722 (*Quercus suber*) forest located in the northeast of the Iberian Peninsula.
723 *Environmental Research* **111**, 237-247.
- 724 Porta J, López-Acevedo M, Roquero C (Eds) (2003) 'Edafología para la agricultura y el
725 medio ambiente.' (Mundiprensa: Madrid)
- 726 Quinn GP, Keough MJ (Eds) (2009) 'Experimental design and data analysis for
727 biologists.' (Cambridge University Press: Cambridge)
- 728 Rademacher P (2005) Contents of nutrient elements in tree components of economical
729 important species in relation to their residual utilisation. *European Journal of*
730 *Wood and Wood Products* **63**, 285-296.
- 731 Raison RJ (1979) Modification of the soil environment by vegetation fires, with
732 particular reference to nitrogen transformations - Review. *Plant and Soil* **51**, 73-
733 108.
- 734 Saarela KE, Harju L, Lill JO, Rajander J, Lindroos A, Heselius SJ, Saari K (2002)
735 Thick-target PIXE analysis of trace elements in wood incoming to a pulp mill.
736 *Holzforschung* **56**, 380-387.
- 737 Sánchez-Marañón M, Delgado R, Párraga J, Delgado G (1996) Multivariate analysis in
738 the quantitative evaluation of soils for reforestation in the Sierra Nevada
739 (southern Spain). *Geoderma* **69**, 233-248.
- 740 Schinner F, Öhlinger R, Kandeler E, Margesin R (Eds) (1995) *Methods in soil biology*.
741 (Springer: Berlin)
- 742 Serrano-Ortiz P, Marañón-Jiménez S, Reverter BR, Sánchez-Cañete EP, Castro J,
743 Zamora R, Kowalski AS (2011) Post-fire salvage logging reduces carbon
744 sequestration in Mediterranean coniferous forest. *Forest Ecology and*
745 *Management* **262**, 2287-2296.

- 746 Shakesby RA (2011) Post-wildfire soil erosion in the Mediterranean: Review and future
747 research directions. *Earth-Science Reviews* **105**, 71-100.
- 748 Silver WL (1998) The potential effects of elevated CO₂ and climate change on tropical
749 forest soils and biochemical cycling. *Climatic Change* **39**, 337-361.
- 750 Sparks DL (Eds) (1996) 'Methods of soil analysis. Part 3. Chemical methods.' (Soil
751 Science Society of America and American Society of Agronomy: Madison)
- 752 Soil Conservation Service (1972) 'Soil survey laboratory methods and procedures for
753 collecting soils samples. Soil survey report 1.' (U.S.D.A.: Washington DC)
- 754 Stocks BJ, Alexander ME, Wotton BM, Steffner CN, Flannigan MD, Taylor SW, Lavoie
755 N, Mason JA, Hartley GR, Maffey ME, Dalrymple GN, Blake TW, Cruz MG,
756 Lanoville RA (2004) Crown fire behaviour in a northern jack pine-black spruce
757 forest. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research-Revue Canadienne De Recherche*
758 *Forestiere* **34**, 1548-1560.
- 759 Thomas AD, Walsh RPD, Shakesby RA (1999) Nutrient losses in eroded sediment after
760 fire in eucalyptus and pine forests in the wet Mediterranean environment of
761 northern Portugal. *Catena* **36**, 283-302.
- 762 Thomas AD, Walsh RPD, Shakesby RA (2000) Post-fire forestry management and
763 nutrient losses in eucalyptus and pine plantations, northern Portugal. *Land*
764 *Degradation & Development* **11**, 257-271.
- 765 Thompson LM, Troeh FR (Eds) (2005) 'Soils and soil fertility.' (Blackwell Publishing:
766 Oxford)
- 767 Tinker DB, Knight DH (2000) Coarse woody debris following fire and logging in
768 Wyoming lodgepole pine forests. *Ecosystems* **3**, 472-483.
- 769 Trabaud L (1994) The effect of fire on nutrient losses and cycling in a *Quercus*
770 *coccifera* garrigue (southern France). *Oecologia* **99**, 379-386.

- 771 van Wesemael B (1993) Litter decomposition and nutrient distribution in humus
772 profiles in some Mediterranean forests in Southern Tuscany. *Forest Ecology and*
773 *Management* **57**, 99-114.
- 774 Wan SQ, Hui DF, Luo YQ (2001) Fire effects on nitrogen pools and dynamics in
775 terrestrial ecosystems: A meta-analysis. *Ecological Applications* **11**, 1349-1365.
- 776 Watanabe S, Olsen RS (1965) Test of an ascorbic acid method for determining
777 phosphorus in water and NaHCO₃ extracts from soil. *Soil Science Society of*
778 *America Journal* **29**, 677-678.
- 779 Wei X, Kimmins JP, Peel K, Steen O (1997) Mass and nutrients in woody debris in
780 harvested and wildfire-killed lodgepole pine forests in the central interior of
781 British Columbia. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research-Revue Canadienne De*
782 *Recherche Forestiere* **27**, 148-155.
- 783 Whelan RJ (Ed) (1995) 'The ecology of fire. Cambridge studies in ecology.'
784 (Cambridge University Press: Cambridge)
- 785 Whittig LD, Allardice WR (1986) X-ray diffraction techniques. In 'Methods of soil
786 analysis, Part 1. Agronomy Monograph 9.' (Ed. A Klute) pp. 331-362 (ASA and
787 SSSA: Madison)
- 788 Yang YS, Guo JF, Chen GS, He ZM, Xie JS (2003) Effect of slash burning on nutrient
789 removal and soil fertility in Chinese fir and evergreen broadleaved forests of
790 mid-subtropical China. *Pedosphere* **13**, 87-96.
- 791 Yildiz O, Esen D, Sarginci M, Toprak B (2010) Effects of forest fire on soil nutrients in
792 Turkish pine (*Pinus brutia*, Ten.) Ecosystems. *Journal of Environmental Biology*
793 **31**, 11-13.
- 794 Zar JH (2010) 'Biostatistical Analysis'. 5th edition. (Prentice Hall: Upper Saddle River,
795 NJ).

796 **Table 1. Main pre-fire stand characteristics and dasometric variables of the trees in the**
 797 **study sites**

Element	Site			
	1	2	3	4
UTM position	456070; 4089811	455449;4091728	457244;4091551	457719; 4091518
Altitude ^A (m above sea level)	1477	1698	2053	2317
Slope	25–30%	25–35%	35%	20%
Pre-fire dominant species	<i>Pinus pinaster</i> Aiton.	<i>Pinus nigra</i> Arnold.	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> L.	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> L.
Tree density (individuals ha ⁻¹)	1477 ± 46	1064 ± 67	1051 ± 42	1058 ± 52
Diameter at 1.30 m (cm)	13.3 ± 0.2	14.5 ± 0.2	10.7 ± 0.2	13.4 ± 0.3
Tree height (m)	6.3 ± 0.1	6.6 ± 0.1	6.2 ± 0.1	6.6 ± 0.2

798 ^AAltitude in the centre of the delimited area of each site.

799

800

801 **Table 2. Nutrient concentrations in the partially charred wood in the four study sites**

802 Values represent means ± standard errors. Different lowercase superscript letters indicate
 803 significant differences among means for sites (Tukey *post-hoc* test after one-way ANOVAs). *F*,
 804 value of the statistic; *P*, critical probability

Nutrients in wood	Site				<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
	1	2	3	4		
C (%) ^A	50.49 ± 0.08	50.60 ± 0.08	50.63 ± 0.07	50.37 ± 0.07	2.46	0.0645
N (%)	0.163 ± 0.004 ^a	0.187 ± 0.006 ^b	0.189 ± 0.005 ^b	0.155 ± 0.005 ^a	11.84	≤ 0.0001
C : N ^A	320.45 ± 8.75 ^a	284.77 ± 10.29 ^b	278.65 ± 9.29 ^b	342.8 ± 12.99 ^a	10.03	≤ 0.0001
N : P ^A	18.90 ± 1.58 ^a	20.04 ± 1.33 ^{a,b}	22.54 ± 1.42 ^b	28.89 ± 1.60 ^c	14.02	≤ 0.0001
P (ppm)	99.74 ± 5.17 ^a	105.42 ± 5.82 ^a	91.49 ± 3.55 ^a	58.74 ± 2.48 ^b	25.95	≤ 0.0001
Ca (ppm) ^A	622.48 ± 43.54 ^a	710.05 ± 48.27 ^a	627.32 ± 35.37 ^a	438.16 ± 19.61 ^b	10.11	≤ 0.0001
Mg (ppm)	264.56 ± 11.57 ^a	264.98 ± 10.12 ^a	233.69 ± 9.49 ^a	186.98 ± 9.47 ^b	13.36	≤ 0.0001
K (ppm) ^B	575.00 ± 36.75 ^a	504.31 ± 27.15 ^a	359.33 ± 18.47 ^b	203.19 ± 13.51 ^c	54.68	≤ 0.0001
Na (ppm) ^B	69.39 ± 4.58 ^a	50.83 ± 2.46 ^{a,b}	40.32 ± 2.56 ^{b,c}	31.03 ± 2.38 ^c	19.67	≤ 0.0001
Fe (ppm) ^B	12.56 ± 2.03 ^a	7.82 ± 1.26 ^{a,b}	7.14 ± 1.21 ^{a,b}	4.85 ± 1.02 ^b	3.912	0.0097
Mn (ppm) ^A	29.79 ± 2 ^a	30.00 ± 1.58 ^a	43.39 ± 2.36 ^b	67.04 ± 3.25 ^c	43.65	≤ 0.0001
Zn (ppm) ^A	4.63 ± 0.52	4.62 ± 0.49	5.302 ± 0.56	3.870 ± 0.51	0.52	0.6711
Cu (ppm)	1.17 ± 0.07 ^a	1.56 ± 0.09 ^b	1.35 ± 0.09 ^{a,b}	1.14 ± 0.07 ^a	5.67	0.001

805 ^ALog-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

806 ^BSquare-root-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

807

808

809

810

811

812

813

814

815

816

817

818

819 **Table 3. Main soil parameters of the study sites**

820 Values represent means \pm standard errors. CEC, cationic exchange capacity; SOM, soil organic
 821 matter; ρ , bulk density. Different lowercase superscript letters indicate significant differences
 822 among means for sites (Tukey *post-hoc* test after one-way ANOVAs, Nemenyi test after
 823 Kruskal–Wallis tests for texture and mineralogy). *F/H*, value of the statistic; *P*, critical
 824 probability

Soil Parameter	Site				<i>F/H</i>	<i>P</i>
	1	2	3	4		
Soil type ^A	Haplic phaeozems	Haplic phaeozems	Haplic phaeozems	Humic cambisols and haplic phaeozems		
ρ (g cm ⁻³) ^B	1.25 \pm 0.06	1.34 \pm 0.07	1.15 \pm 0.06	1.18 \pm 0.04	2.15	0.1006
Texture (%)	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam		
Sand (2–0.05 mm)	59.4 \pm 2.4	58.9 \pm 3.2	69.0 \pm 0.1	69.1 \pm 0.7	8.44	0.0378
Coarse loam (0.05–0.02 mm)	10.6 \pm 0.8 ^{a,b}	11.9 \pm 0.7 ^a	9.7 \pm 0.4 ^{a,b}	7.3 \pm 0.2 ^b	8.44	0.0378
Fine loam (0.02– 0.002 mm)	15.2 \pm 0.7	16.7 \pm 1.3	12.5 \pm 0.4	13.6 \pm 0.5	8.95	0.0300
Clay (<0.002 mm)	14.8 \pm 0.9 ^a	12.5 \pm 1.5 ^{a,b}	8.8 \pm 0.3 ^b	10.0 \pm 0.3 ^{a,b}	8.74	0.0329
Mineralogy (%)						
Quartz	17 \pm 3	20 \pm 3	17 \pm 2	19 \pm 2	1.31	0.7273
Clorite (Clinocllore)	4 \pm 0.2	3 \pm 1	16 \pm 3	19 \pm 2	8.43	0.0378
Muscovite	51 \pm 2	43 \pm 4	44 \pm 2	50 \pm 1	4.53	0.2089
Paragonite	15 \pm 1 ^{a,b}	18 \pm 2 ^a	12 \pm 2 ^{a,b}	7 \pm 1 ^b	9.15	0.0273
Feldespat (Albite)	13 \pm 2 ^{a,b}	15 \pm 2 ^a	10 \pm 1 ^{a,b}	5 \pm 0.5 ^b	8.08	0.0444
pH ^C	7.27 \pm 0.04 ^a	7.28 \pm 0.05 ^a	6.71 \pm 0.08 ^b	5.58 \pm 0.10 ^c	83.66	\leq 0.0001
SOM (%) ^B	3.34 \pm 0.19 ^a	3.32 \pm 0.18 ^a	3.57 \pm 0.18 ^a	6.04 \pm 0.17 ^b	48.79	\leq 0.0001
CEC (Cmol ⁺ kg ⁻¹)	5.59 \pm 0.26 ^a	5.31 \pm 0.31 ^a	4.63 \pm 0.31 ^a	8.19 \pm 0.27 ^b	29.71	\leq 0.0001

825 ^ASoil types according to the soil map: Lanjarón 1:100 000. LUCDEME Project (Delgado Calvo-Flores
 826 *et al.* 1993).

827 ^BLog-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

828 ^CExponential-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

829

830

831

832

833

834

835

836

837

838

839

840
841
842
843
844
845

846 **Table 4. Soil nutrient concentrations in the four study sites**

847 Values represent means \pm standard errors. V, percentage of bases saturation; C_{tot} and N_{tot}, soil C
848 and N referred to total concentrations, Different lowercase superscript letters indicate significant
849 differences among means for sites (Tukey *post-hoc* test after one-ways ANOVAs). *F*, value of
850 the statistic; *P*, critical probability

Element	Site				F	P
	1	2	3	4		
C _{tot} (%) ^C	1.05 \pm 0.11 ^a	1.17 \pm 0.10 ^a	1.30 \pm 0.13 ^a	2.98 \pm 0.09 ^b	44.63	\leq 0.0001
N _{tot} (%) ^C	0.06 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.07 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.09 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.20 \pm 0.01 ^c	73.49	\leq 0.0001
C : N ^C	16.36 \pm 0.72 ^a	17.42 \pm 0.68 ^a	13.32 \pm 0.68 ^b	14.65 \pm 0.68 ^{a,b}	6.77	0.0004
NH ₄ ⁺ (ppm) ^A	2.52 \pm 0.80	3.10 \pm 0.82	3.66 \pm 0.85	2.62 \pm 0.88	0.39	0.7591
NO ₃ ⁻ (ppm) ^A	0.81 \pm 0.24	1.17 \pm 0.35	1.47 \pm 0.28	2.14 \pm 0.44	2.69	0.0521
N _{inorg} : N _{tot} (%)	0.63 \pm 0.18	0.80 \pm 0.25	0.54 \pm 0.12	0.23 \pm 0.06	2.12	0.1054
P _{inog} (ppm) ^{A,C}	4.96 \pm 1.25 ^{a,b}	1.87 \pm 0.15 ^c	2.64 \pm 0.38 ^{b,c}	5.40 \pm 0.59 ^a	10.12	\leq 0.0001
Ca (Cmol+ kg ⁻¹) ^B	3.24 \pm 0.24 ^a	3.14 \pm 0.23 ^a	1.70 \pm 0.23 ^b	2.40 \pm 0.23 ^{a,b}	9.13	\leq 0.0001
Mg (Cmol+ kg ⁻¹) ^{B,D}	1.31 \pm 0.07 ^a	1.04 \pm 0.06 ^a	0.65 \pm 0.06 ^b	0.72 \pm 0.06 ^b	20.97	\leq 0.0001
K (Cmol+ kg ⁻¹) ^B	0.019 \pm 0.002	0.022 \pm 0.001	0.018 \pm 0.001	0.023 \pm 0.001	2.05	0.1141
Na (Cmol+ kg ⁻¹) ^B	0.0021 \pm 0.0007	0.0022 \pm 0.0007	0.0012 \pm 0.0007	0.0017 \pm 0.0007	0.49	0.6900
V (%)	81.81 \pm 5.40 ^a	82.60 \pm 5.12 ^a	55.62 \pm 5.12 ^b	38.89 \pm 5.12 ^b	16.93	\leq 0.0001
Fe (ppm) ^B	0.060 \pm 0.029	0.089 \pm 0.034	0.091 \pm 0.034	0.025 \pm 0.015	1.18	0.3227
Mn (ppm) ^{B,D}	0.37 \pm 0.08 ^a	0.36 \pm 0.05 ^a	0.65 \pm 0.09 ^{a,b}	0.95 \pm 0.17 ^b	6.25	0.0008
Zn (ppm) ^B	0.026 \pm 0.010	0.025 \pm 0.008	0.032 \pm 0.009	0.009 \pm 0.005	1.46	0.2321
Cu (ppm) ^B	0.015 \pm 0.007	0.017 \pm 0.008	0.014 \pm 0.007	0.005 \pm 0.005	0.55	0.6484

851 ^AExtractable concentrations.

852 ^BExchangeable concentrations.

853 ^CLog-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

854 ^DSquare-root-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

855
856 **Fig. 1.** Location of the study area and relative geographical position of the study sites. (a) Iberian
857 peninsula, (b) Granada province, (c) Sierra Nevada (Spain).

858
 859 **Fig. 2.** Principal component analysis (PCA) of wood nutrient concentrations (*a* and *b*), and soil nutrient
 860 concentrations (*c* and *d*) in the four different study sites. For an easier visualisation, only the two first
 861 principal components are represented. The percentage of contribution to the total variability is between
 862 parentheses. (*a*) and (*c*) show the relative contribution of each individual variable to the first two principal
 863 components; (*b*) and (*d*) show the value assigned to each wood sample according to these two
 864 components. Data were previously log- or square-root-transformed when required to improve normality
 865 and homoscedasticity (see footnotes in [Tables 3, 4](#)).

866
 867 **Fig. 3.** Nutrient reservoir in the charred wood and soil pools: (a) nutrient content in the aboveground
 868 wood biomass left after the wildfire and in the upper-10-cm soil layer; (b) nutrient percentage relative to
 869 the total content in the wood and soil pools. Nitrogen in the soil pool is referred to the extractable
 870 inorganic fraction ($\text{NH}_4^+ + \text{NO}_3^-$). Needles and branches <2 cm were excluded due to their total
 871 combustion during the fire. Values of nutrient content are the mean of the four experimental sites,
 872 standard errors are represented above each bar. Note in (a) the different scale of each graph and the
 873 breaks in Ca for better visualisation.

874

875

876 Appendix

877

878 **Fig. A1.** Rain events occurred 9 months after the fire. The graph shows the rainfall pattern between the
 879 fire and the collection date of wood samples (6 months after the wildfire) and soil samples (2 years after
 880 the wildfire). Data from a meteorological station beside the lowest site.

881

882

883

884

885

886

887

888

889

890

891

892

893

894

895

896

897

898

899

900

901

902

903

904

905

906

907

908 **Table A1. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients between each pair of wood**
 909 **nutrients**

910 Values indicate the coefficients of each correlation. Data from all sites are pooled. Critical
 911 probabilities of the correlations (P) are indicated: *, $0.01 < P \leq 0.05$; **, $0.001 < P \leq 0.01$; ***,
 912 $P \leq 0.001$

Variable	C ^A	N	P ^B	Ca ^A	Mg	K ^B	Na ^B	Fe ^B	Mn ^A	Zn ^A	Cu
C ^A	1										
N	0.26***	1									
P ^B	-0.07	0.29***	1								
Ca ^A	0.15*	0.25***	0.28***	1							
Mg	0.11	0.27***	0.43***	0.41***	1						
K ^B	0.02	0.26***	0.75***	0.22**	0.54***	1					
Na ^B	-0.01	0.08	0.51***	-0.06	0.36***	0.59***	1				
Fe ^B	0.22**	0.06	0.19**	0.17*	0.28***	0.26***	0.24***	1			
Mn ^A	-0.01	0.13	-0.23**	-0.25***	-0.23**	-0.39***	-0.13	0.04	1		
Zn ^A	0.13	0.22**	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.02	-0.04	0.33***	0.18*	1	
Cu	0.24**	0.22**	0.33***	0.20**	0.23**	0.18*	0.13	0.36***	0.06	0.18*	1

913 ^ALog-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

914 ^BSquare-root-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

915
 916
 917
 918
 919
 920
 921
 922
 923
 924
 925
 926
 927
 928
 929
 930
 931
 932
 933
 934
 935
 936
 937
 938
 939
 940
 941
 942
 943
 944
 945
 946

947 **Table A2. Pearson product- moment correlations coefficients between each pair of soil**
 948 **variables**

949 Values indicate the coefficients of each correlation. Data of all sites are pooled. Critical
 950 probabilities of the correlations (P) are indicated: *, $0.01 < P \leq 0.05$; **, $0.001 < P \leq 0.01$; ***,
 951 $P \leq 0.001$

variable	pH ^A	SOM ^B	CEC	C _{tot} ^B	N _{tot} ^B	NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻	P _{inorg} ^B	Ca	Mg ^C	K	Na	Fe	Mn ^C	Zn	Cu
pH ^A	1															
SOM ^B	-0.67***	1														
CEC	-0.46***	0.81***	1													
C _{tot} ^B	-0.70***	0.94***	0.78***	1												
N _{tot} ^B	-0.78***	0.90***	0.69***	0.93***	1											
NH ₄ ⁺	0.05	0.03	-0.01	0.01	-0.02	1										
NO ₃ ⁻	-0.23*	0.33**	0.23*	0.29**	0.27*	0.75***	1									
P _{inorg} ^B	-0.35**	0.55***	0.60***	0.62***	0.55***	-0.05	0.13	1								
Ca	0.41***	0.11	0.19	0.05	-0.13	-0.09	-0.08	0.06	1							
Mg ^C	0.57***	-0.09	0.10	-0.18	-0.33**	0.02	-0.09	-0.01	0.78***	1						
K	-0.05	0.31**	0.25*	0.39***	0.34**	-0.02	0.01	0.40***	0.35**	0.25*	1					
Na	0.12	-0.04	-0.04	-0.10	-0.07	-0.09	-0.18	-0.10	0.24*	0.19	0.18	1				
Fe	0.20	-0.09	-0.13	-0.07	-0.15	0.03	-0.03	-0.11	0.30**	0.14	-0.10	0.04	1			
Mn ^C	-0.37***	0.45***	0.35**	0.51***	0.46***	-0.11	-0.10	0.44***	0.11	-0.10	0.34**	0.10	0.18	1		
Zn	0.14	-0.25*	-0.14	-0.23*	-0.23*	-0.22*	-0.20	-0.15	-0.01	-0.03	-0.11	-0.12	0.24*	0.05	1	
Cu	0.11	0.01	0.06	0.04	-0.07	-0.20	-0.17	0.01	0.26*	0.21	-0.01	-0.10	0.59***	0.29*	0.35**	1

952 ^AExponential-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

953 ^BLog-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

954 ^CSquare-root-transformed data before ANOVA tests.

955